

Deliverable 1.2

Dissemination and Exploitation Plans

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1.2	Dissemination and Exploitation Plans
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3. Background to the LegumES project

The legumES will ensure:

1. the uptake of best practices in agrobiodiverse legume-based cropped systems;
2. the uptake of methodologies and tools to quantify and balance the environmental and economic ecosystem service (ES) benefits provided by legumes;
3. that the ES benefits and costs offered by legumes are quantified across scales from field, farm, regional, national, and global levels; and
4. ES will be assessed to identify those conditions which are able to meet the EU targets: to decrease agrichemical inputs and losses, combat climate change, reverse biodiversity loss, and ensure the best nutritional provisioning.

To achieve this, legumES offers a multi-disciplinary consortium comprising 22 partners from 12 EU- and third countries (UK, CH) and including: 7, academic institutions; 6, Research and Technology Organizations; 5, SMEs (or micro-SMEs); 2, non-governmental organisations; and 2, large commercial companies. The individuals comprising legumES offer skills which include: agricultural-crop and -environment (ES) monitoring, life cycle assessment, economic- and socioeconomic-modelling, social-science, EU-agricultural and environmental policy, and law, plus decision support systems. The legumES research and innovation strategy centres on the use of a multiactor action-research approach, that is, where legume-facing stakeholders, and especially producers though all value chains actors, can 'operate', 'collaborate' and, 'reflect critically' on the measured ES benefits and costs of legume-based cropped systems, including legumes use in marginal lands; so that an optimal balance of ES can be achieved with success locally, and globally. To help achieve this, LegumES also centres activities on a suite of 25 innovative legume-based Pilot Studies which use a wide range of legume species and types, plus different cropping approaches and linked value chains spanning the pedoclimatic regions of Europe.

For more information on the project, see:

- [Valorising and balancing the ecosystem service benefits offered by legumes, and legume-based cropped systems | LegumES | Project | Fact sheet | HORIZON |CORDIS | European Commission](#)
- www.legumESproject.eu

4. Executive Summary

To maximize legumES' impacts, special attention has been paid from early in the project, to successfully disseminate, exploit, and communicate the project results within the EU, EU-Associated Countries and beyond. LegumES' Dissemination and Exploitation strategies are complementary and synergistic, targeting a wide range of stakeholders.

- Our **Dissemination and Communication Strategy** are focusing on providing a reliable, smooth, and efficient knowledge transfer of legumES outputs and innovations and communication of project activities, which are targeted and tailored to intended project actors and audiences. Hence, it details our approach and objectives, target groups and how these will be reached. It also outlines our plans for open access.
- Our **Exploitation Strategy** aims to ensure that all outputs of the project will be used for the benefit of the partners, stakeholders, and society at large, thus generating impact. Hence, an effective innovation management system (comprising a set of tools and a reporting system) has been developed, with plans for its implementation currently being formulated. Annual exploitation workshops will raise awareness among project participants for exploitation and assist the result owner to develop tailored exploitation strategies.

The Dissemination and Exploitation strategies also include the **Communication Handbook**, which outlines the communication tools and materials used within the project. It also describes the branding and rules to follow when communicating the project results (Appendix 1).

The Dissemination and Exploitation strategies will be reviewed annually and updated as necessary throughout the project lifetime to ensure that they remain fit-for-purpose to maximize the impact of the project.

1. Dissemination Strategy

The Dissemination strategy is a carefully planned blueprint designed to communicate the results, outcomes, and impacts of a project to a wide range of stakeholders. It should outline the methods and channels that will be used to share information, engage with target audiences to ensure the project's findings are widely promoted, understood, and utilized. Hence, the primary goal of a dissemination plan is to maximize the reach and impact of the project's outputs, facilitating knowledge transfer and encouraging the adoption of project innovations.

For the LegumES project, the dissemination plan is critical to ensure a reliable, smooth, and efficient knowledge transfer of legumES innovations and outputs towards the end-users and other target groups. Hence, addressing the six basic questions (who, what, why, when, where, and how), the Dissemination Plan defines our target audience and the tools that will be used to reach each group.

To review the effectiveness of the planned dissemination activities, a suitable evaluation mechanism and KPI analysis will be applied and updated (if/as necessary) during the project implementation.

During the first six months of the project the consortium agreed upon a clear timetable and dissemination methodology (see Appendix 2 for more details). The timetable, together with the dissemination guidelines will ensure an efficient and transparent creation process.

1.1. Objective and Approach

To ensure maximum impact of the project results, LegumES will share research results with the scientific community, commercial players, civil society, and policymakers in accordance with Objective 1.3 from the Grant Agreement (Description of Action – Annex 1).

'Disseminate project results to production agents, and a diverse array of value chain stakeholders from farm to fork, raising consumer awareness of legume-based environmental and personal health benefits.'

This will be achieved using the following approach:

- a **dissemination methodology** established in consultation with project partners to ensure active contribution and early adoption from all work packages to guarantee optimum dissemination;
- easy, fast, and open access to a wide range of **practical tools and materials**;
- **training/guidelines** for partners related to video-making, practice abstracts and other dissemination tools;
- use of an **open access repository** to ensure long-term availability of open-access results and communication/dissemination materials;
- use existing **communication and dissemination channels** at a national and European level (e.g., EIP-Agri, EU FarmBook, Organic Farm Knowledge, FAO communities of practice) to ensure widespread dissemination; and,
- exchange with other relevant **initiatives**, potentially establishing joint initiatives beyond the framework of the projects.

1.2. Target Audience and Messages

The LegumES project's dissemination strategy aims to engage a diverse array of target groups to maximise its economic, societal, and scientific impact. Identifying and understanding these groups is crucial for tailoring our communication efforts and ensuring effective knowledge transfer. By strategically involving these groups, we aim to foster early adoption, promote the practical application of project results, and ensure the project's legacy beyond its lifetime. Table 1 outlines the key target groups identified for the project.

LegumES also aims to communicate tailored messages to each target group to ensure they understand the benefits and applications of sustainable legume cultivation. Specific messages we intend to convey to each target group and ways these can effectively capture the attention of our target audiences are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. List of LegumES' expected Target Audience

Target Group	Importance of the target and how can they benefit	Message to be conveyed
Farmers	<p>Importance: Farmers are the primary beneficiaries of the LegumES project as they are directly involved in legume cultivation. Their adoption of sustainable practices is crucial for the project's success.</p> <p>Benefits: Farmers will gain access to improved farming techniques and crop varieties, leading to higher yields, reduced costs, and enhanced soil health. This will ultimately improve their economic stability and environmental sustainability.</p>	<p>Intent: Communicate the practical benefits of adopting sustainable legume cultivation techniques, such as increased yields, cost savings, and improved soil health and ecosystem functions.</p> <p>Engagement Strategy: Use hands-on workshops, field demonstrations, and success stories from fellow farmers (including participatory farmer trials) to illustrate the tangible benefits and provide actionable guidance.</p>
Agronomists	<p>Importance: Agronomists play a vital role in advising and supporting farmers with scientific and practical knowledge about crop production and soil management.</p> <p>Benefits: They will benefit from the latest research findings and innovations in legume cultivation, enabling them to provide better guidance to farmers, improve crop management practices, and enhance overall agricultural productivity.</p>	<p>Intent: Highlight the latest research findings and innovative techniques in legume cultivation, positioning them as essential resources for advancing agricultural practices.</p> <p>Engagement Strategy: Share detailed research reports, host webinars and seminars, and facilitate direct interactions with leading scientists involved in the project, for example through the Pilot Studies and Living Labs.</p>
Ag-science Researchers and Educators	<p>Importance: Researchers and educators are key to advancing scientific knowledge and training the next generation of agricultural professionals.</p> <p>Benefits: They will have access to new data, case studies, and practical applications that can be integrated into research projects and educational curricula, fostering innovation and improving the quality of agricultural education and research.</p>	<p>Intent: Provide access to comprehensive data, case studies, and educational materials that can be used to advance their research and teaching in sustainable agriculture.</p> <p>Engagement Strategy: Offer academic publications and research presentations, create educational modules, and organize conferences to disseminate knowledge and encourage collaboration.</p>
Environmental Agencies, Regulatory bodies	<p>Importance: Environmental agencies are responsible for protecting natural resources and promoting sustainable practices.</p> <p>Benefits: They will benefit from the project's findings on sustainable agricultural practices, which can inform policies and programs aimed at reducing environmental impact, enhancing biodiversity, and promoting soil conservation.</p>	<p>Intent: Demonstrate the environmental benefits of sustainable legume cultivation, such as biodiversity enhancement and soil conservation, to support policy and program development.</p> <p>Engagement Strategy: Provide evidence-based reports, presentations, case studies, and policy briefs that showcase the positive environmental impacts of the project.</p>
Stakeholders	<p>Importance: Stakeholders, including industry partners, NGOs, and community organizations, are essential for the broad dissemination and implementation of project outcomes.</p>	<p>Intent: Encourage collaboration and support by showcasing the project's innovative approaches and the broader societal benefits of sustainable agriculture.</p>

Target Group	Importance of the target and how can they benefit	Message to be conveyed
	<p>Benefits: They will gain insights into sustainable practices and innovations that can be applied within their networks, contributing to wider community benefits and supporting collective action towards sustainability.</p>	<p>Engagement Strategy: Use networking events, partnership opportunities (including Pilot Study Living Labs), and regular updates through newsletters and dedicated meetings to keep stakeholders informed and involved.</p>
Sustainable-business Advisors	<p>Importance: Sustainable-business advisors help businesses integrate sustainable practices into their operations, ensuring long-term viability and environmental responsibility.</p> <p>Benefits: They will be equipped with the latest sustainable agricultural practices and innovations from the project, which they can use to advise clients in the agri-food sector, leading to more sustainable and profitable business models.</p>	<p>Intent: Equip advisors with insights and tools to help their clients in the agri-food sector adopt sustainable practices, leading to more resilient and eco-friendly business models.</p> <p>Engagement Strategy: Develop comprehensive toolkits, best practice guides, and case study examples to demonstrate the business case for sustainability.</p>
Consumers/General public	<p>Importance: Consumers drive demand for sustainable products and practices, influencing the entire food supply chain.</p> <p>Benefits: They will benefit from greater access to sustainably produced legumes, which are healthier and environmentally friendly. Increased awareness of sustainable agriculture can also drive consumer support for eco-friendly products, promoting a more sustainable food system.</p>	<p>Intent: Raise awareness about the health and environmental benefits of sustainably produced legumes, driving consumer demand for these products.</p> <p>Engagement Strategy: Use social media campaigns, informative videos, and partnerships with influencers to educate consumers and promote sustainably produced legume products.</p>
Policymakers (National, EU)	<p>Importance: Policymakers are crucial for creating the regulatory and support framework needed to implement and sustain agricultural innovations.</p> <p>Benefits: They will have access to evidence-based recommendations and data from the project, aiding in the development of policies that support sustainable agriculture, environmental protection, and rural development. This can lead to long-term positive impacts on food security and environmental sustainability.</p>	<p>Intent: Provide policymakers with data and recommendations to support the development of policies that promote sustainable agriculture and food security.</p> <p>Engagement Strategy: Prepare policy briefs, organize policy dialogue sessions, and inform policymakers on current understanding to ensure they understand the project's findings and their implications.</p>

1.3. Dissemination tools and channels

Dissemination tools are resources or methods used to share information, ideas, products, or services with a broader audience. These tools aim to facilitate the distribution and dissemination of specific messages. Hence, they contribute to making the content accessible to the target audience and increase its visibility. In LegumES, several formats will be used to disseminate the project results to the target audiences (Table 2).

Table 2. The main dissemination activities to be used in LegumES.

Activities/Tools	Target Group
Participation in external events: Partners will participate in relevant events, fairs & conferences, where activities and results will be widely showcased (presentations, posters, workshops...).	Research & Academia; Policy Makers; EU projects/networks; farmers, industry, and General public
LegumES Events: National Multiactor Workshops (12), Tasting-Cocreation Workshops (5), National Cooperation Workshops (4), Innovation Camps (3), international symposium organized to disseminate the project results (1).	Research & Academia; Stakeholders, EU projects/networks and Policy makers (or related organizations)
Publications (scientific and non-scientific): Scientific publications in (peer-reviewed) journals (gold or green open access) and sector specific magazines. Presentations in specialized conferences will ensure knowledge transmission/exchange with the scientific and technical community.	Scientific and technical Communities, Advisors, Farmers, Industry
Training and Dissemination materials: Partners will explain the project and its results to various audiences through dedicated platforms and popular articles and blogs published in online national and international magazines.	Farmers, Advisors, Students, Policy makers, General Public
Clustering with other projects/Initiatives and discussion forums: Organize shared and common promotion activities with sister projects (e.g., joint symposia or EU parliamentary sessions, joint dissemination materials, etc.) to optimize resources, reach a wider audience and maximize the impact of the proposed actions.	Other EU projects/networks, citizens, farmers, advisors, public authorities/policy makers
Policy briefs: Results and main conclusions of the project will be compiled and summarized in recommendations for policy makers to influence future policy and regulatory actions. These will be presented at the EU Parliamentary session to be organized by LegumES.	Policy makers, regulation bodies, public administrations
Official EU Key Tools as the Horizon Results Platform, ENOLL, EU Result Booster, CORDIS, EU-FarmBook, and EU magazines	EU projects/networks, stakeholders representatives at EU-level and policy makers

In addition, to ensure the broadest reach, dissemination materials will be **translated** where relevant and disseminated by partners as well as through social media, the project website, sister projects, relevant existing channels (e.g., EIP Agri, EU FarmBook, FAO communities of practice, Organic Farm Knowledge) and the stakeholder advisory board.

To ensure knowledge transmission with the scientific and technical community, **scientific publications** will be submitted to peer-reviewed journals and stored in the open-access repository Zenodo.

Similarly, **conference presentations** (conference abstracts and posters) and presentation at **other relevant events** (field visits, industry meetings, etc.) will widely disseminate and promote the project’s results.

Results and main conclusions of the project will be compiled and presented at the **international LegumES symposium**. They will also be summarised in **recommendations for policy makers** to influence future policy and regulatory actions. These will be presented at one **EU Parliamentary session** in 2027 to be organized by LegumES.

A detailed introduction to the different dissemination materials as well as guidelines for partners and templates can be found in Appendix 2.

1.4. Open access

Horizon Europe projects must ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to results. The LegumES project is also committed to making all its outputs and other publications available open access. For this purpose, a [LegumES community](#) was established on **Zenodo**. This will ensure open access to all publications and other tools and materials, including factsheets, infographics, non-scientific articles, videos, conference contributions and presentations.

For **scientific publications**, either green or gold access will be chosen. LegumES partners will deposit the accepted version of their manuscript to Zenodo before it is published on the journal website. They will ensure immediate open access to the publications. Partners will be reminded that *‘Only publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.’*

Partners are also reminded that scientific publications can be published through the [Open Research Europe platform](#), an open access, publishing platform for scientific papers for Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe beneficiaries, which features an open peer review and article revision procedure.

For more information about using scientific publication workflow, see Appendix 2. In addition, guidelines to upload outputs on Zenodo have been created. These are available on the project [SharePoint](#).

1.5. Evaluation

Key performance indicators (KPIs) have been agreed upon for the various dissemination activities (Table 3). The KPIs will be monitored at the end of each reporting period to ensure that there are no deviations. We will use the project review to collect feedback from project participants and implement modifications to the strategy and plan if necessary.

Table 3. Key performance indicators for each dissemination activities/tools.

Activities/Tools	KPIs
Participation in external events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > 10 international events > 40 national/regional events > 40,000 people (audience)

Activities/Tools	KPIs
LegumES Events	> 27 workshops/knowledge transfer/training/ events organized 3 Innovation Camps 1 international symposium organized 1 EU Parliamentary Session > 250 attendees
Publications (scientific and non-scientific)	> 10 published articles (peer reviewed) > 25 conference presentations > 10 publications in sector specific magazines
Training and Dissemination materials	42 Practice Abstracts (EIP-AGRI) and associated factsheets > 10 practice oriented short videos (tutorials) > 10 practice-oriented podcasts > 10 practice-oriented Infographics
Clustering with other projects/Initiatives and discussion forums	> 5 joint actions within identified networks and other H2020/ HE projects
Policy briefs	2 Policy Briefs
Official EU Key Tools	> 3 Publications/Activities

1.6. Barriers & Risks

The main risks and barriers to successful communication of project activities and dissemination of findings relate to stakeholder engagement, workflow barriers and disruption to knowledge exchange events.

Failure to engage/retain stakeholders. Stakeholder engagement is a priority from the project outset; stakeholders will be given appropriate information to understand the purposes and progress of the project, and stakeholder collaboration is hard-wired into project activities, including dissemination. This is particularly important for engaging farmers in the participatory farmer call. We will build on existing relationships between partners and their stakeholder networks, inviting them to take part in co-creation and co-innovation work to achieve mutually desired goals. Partners have established links to farmers and farmer networks and existing experience of engaging farmers in participatory research. This participatory approach will ensure that stakeholders continue to feel valued throughout and beyond the project. In addition, strong coordination between WP1 and WP2 will create engagement in all stages of the project, and partner networks will be used to reach out to actors and especially policymakers at national, regional, and local levels.

Delays in work plan and outputs. These might arise due to inter-dependencies between tasks and/or WPs, with follow-on consequences for planned dissemination activities. Mitigations include quarterly monthly internal progress reports to allow early identification and mitigation of delays. If required, we will implement shorter monitoring intervals with more detailed incremental deadlines, reallocate tasks/responsibilities or rework/adjust timeline, and involve additional partners with relevant expertise.

Global events disrupt dissemination activities. A global pandemic, acts of aggression and extreme weather could disrupt or delay planned events. If the effects are long-lasting, the experience during the global COVID-19 pandemic has equipped partners and most stakeholders with the skills and capacity for alternative methods of knowledge exchange and transfer, capitalizing on the many different online platforms and media available at relatively low cost.

2. Communication Strategy

The implementation of legumES relies on an effective Communication Strategy, which is closely linked to the strategies for the dissemination and exploitation of results. In the case of legumES, the strategy of ‘Press Office’ will be followed, based on based on the following methodology.

- **Definition of the Messages** - To structure and prepare the strategic messages that allow to position the project in the media panorama.
- **Domain of Information** - Prepare and capitalize upon specific spokespeople to promote/defend the messages in the media. Generate information with interest and differentiation (themes and formats) that help achieve the defined objectives, directly impacting the targets.
- **Increase of Notoriety** - Plan of maximum projection of the dynamics of the project to achieve recognition and offer continuity of its image in the mind of the different audiences.
- **Activities to develop** - Press releases, interviews, and opinion articles.

This strategy will achieve the global transfer of knowledge to the legumES target audiences. Each partner must appoint a communication and dissemination champion officer to oversee the implementation of the communication strategy.

2.1. Communication Channels

To effectively reach our diverse target groups, the LegumES project will utilize a variety of communication channels (Table 4). Each channel is strategically selected to ensure maximum engagement and impact, tailored to the preferences, and needs of different audiences. By leveraging both traditional and digital platforms, we aim to communicate project findings, encourage stakeholder participation, and foster widespread adoption of sustainable practices.

Table 4. Main communication channels to be used by LegumES and associated KPIs.

Channel	Description	KPIs
Website	This attractive and user-friendly website will serve as an info. hub providing an overview of legumES activities, news, events, repository for capacity-building resources practice (e.g. abstracts, models and tools, public deliverables, innovation factsheets etc.).	> 5,000 visitors 50 items uploaded

Channel	Description	KPIs
Social Media	Specific social networks profiles (such as Facebook , Instagram , X , LinkedIn) have been created, and all partners are expected provide content.	> 500 followers in social networks > 5 influencers engaged
Audio-visual Materials	Communication materials (e.g., graphics and multi-media materials) will be produced, that will be centralized in a branding guideline document and updated regularly to adapt to different messages communicated to different audiences.	2 general leaflets/brochures 3 general infographics 2 promotional videos 3 short videos targeted to Social Networks > 2,500 views
Digital & Press media	Digital campaigns for the promotion of the project progress and results will be planned. The campaigns will be promoted through the website, social networks, and dissemination events. Press Releases will emphasize the legumES vision and key results (focused on research but also on the social impact).	3 communication campaigns (5% increase in followers and 5 articles in the popular press per campaign)
Partners' channels	Access to partners existing communication channels such as their websites, social networks accounts, etc.	> 10,000 people as a potential audience to be reached

A Communication Handbook has been produced for partners to easily access simple and clear communication guidelines that feature a Book of Style, and 'Translation' guidance, plus useful resources, which are ready to be used (Appendix 1).

2.2. Communication Monitoring

To facilitate monitoring and assessment of the impact of the communication actions, key performance indicators have been set (Table 4). The KPIs will be monitored at the end of each reporting period to ensure that these will be reached by the end of the project.

3. Exploitation Plan

LegumES adopts the EC terminology to differentiate in between outputs, results and (key) exploitable results. The Horizon Europe Glossary defines **Output** as:

“A specific output of the project, meaningful in terms of the project’s overall objectives in the form of a report, document, technical diagram, piece of software, etc. It should usually be reported on and submitted to the European Commission through the relevant IT platform.”

Outputs can become results or (key) exploitable results (ER) e.g. through further developments during the project. According to the Horizon 2020 Annotated Model Grant Agreement: (EC 2019 - H2020), a **Result** is defined as:

“Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights”.

The Horizon Results Platform Team (EC 2020) describes a **Key Exploitable Result (KER)** as:

“an identified main interesting result (as defined above) which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.”

Exploitation means the use of results in further innovation and research activities other than those covered by LegumES, including commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing, and marketing a product or process, creating, and providing a service, or in standardisation activities. Exploitation includes non-commercial uses such as those results used to influence policy or decision making or non-commercial teaching or training activities. Tangible outputs may include spinoffs, licensed co-products, and Intellectual Property (IP) protection of ERs and KERs, but also extended stakeholder interaction (and use of exploitable results) along with supporting the use of data in future research. It is a legal obligation for all partners and outlined in the Grant Agreement (Article 16 and Annex 5) and Consortium Agreement.

The **aim of this Exploitation Plan** and the activities described herein are to monitor and report exploitable results (ERs), to select key exploitable results (KERs) arising from LegumES, and to support the owners (developers/researchers), of both ERs and KERs in their understanding and development of specific exploitation activities.

To ensure effective exploitation of results, LegumES’ Task 7.4 is dedicated entirely to Innovation-management and exploitation.

Exploitation

Legal obligation:
Article 16 and
Annex 5 of the
Grant Agreement

➔ Make concrete use of results for Commercial, Societal, Political Purposes

Target:

Not only by researchers, but also:

- Industry including SMEs
- Those that can make good use of them, e.g. authorities, policymakers, sectors of interest, civil society

Why?

- Lead to new legislation or recommendations
- For the benefit of innovation, the economy and the society

When?

Towards the end and beyond, as soon as the action has exploitable result

How?

- Creating roadmaps, prototypes, softwares
- Sharing knowledge, skills, data

What? Standards, Policy change, Product Service, Spin-off/ Start-up, Further research

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What else?

Acknowledge the EU funding!

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Figure 1. Picture taken during the Kick-off Meeting in Porto summarising the need for exploitation.

3.1. Innovation Management

Task 7.4 is dedicated entirely to Innovation-management and exploitation. The **Innovation Database** will serve as a central tool for innovation management. The Exploitation Manager (EM) together with result owner(s) and the IPR Management Team (see section 1.3.4) will periodically assesses both exploitation potential and IP throughout the project. The following subsections describe in more details the process.

3.1.1. Monitoring tools

AWI developed an internal, MS Office-based reporting tool for Work Package and Pilot Study leaders to report on the developments of their outputs and results in 6-monthly intervals (Figure 2 and Figure 3). The data provided in these reports will be collated in an MS Excel-based **Innovation Database** (Figure 4). It will summarise all relevant information on all of **LegumES'** outputs (results, ERs and (KERs)). During the first month of the project this information is limited to

- its origin;
- output type;
- a description;
- its potential to become a commercial product;
- estimated percentage of completeness of the work on the output within legumES;
- the current TRL, expected TRL by the end of the project;
- start and end date of the work on the output within legumES;
- details on the owner of the output; and,
- list of contributors to the output.

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Education and Research EAE
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

Over the course of the project additional information will be gathered (see section 1.3.2 and section 1.3.3).

Summary of progress report for Work Package (WP)													
1													
Date of report:		xx.xx.xxxx											
Work Package name:		Multi-actor engagement, co-creation, and capacity building											
Work Package Leader Name:		Insert name											

WPT #	WP Subtasks (WPST)	Name WPT	Reports to task(s)	Task Leader (Name)	Partners involved	Completeness [%]	Risk Status	Start month		End month		TRL	
								planned	actual	planned	actual	Current	by M48
1.1	1.1.1	Analysis with stakeholders of barriers and opportunities for regional legume value	Task xx	?	All Partners	0%	0%	M 1	M xx	M 44	M xx	xx	xx
1.1	1.1.2	Analysis with stakeholders of barriers and opportunities for regional legume value	Task xx	?	All Partners	0%	0%	M 1	M xx	M 44	M xx	xx	xxx
1.2	-	LegumES knowledge and innovation showcase	Task xx	?	All Partners	0%	0%	M 1	M xx	M 48	M xx	xx	xx
1.3	1.3.1	Capacity building for actors in legume production and valorization	Task xx	?	JHI, ADAS, DIL, ZALF, AWI, AgKiu, UCP, TI, SEGES, UniPG, SOL, APRIL, SOL	0%	0%	M 10	M xx	M 46	M xx	xx	xx
1.3	1.3.2	Capacity building for actors in legume production and valorization	Task xx	?	JHI, ADAS, DIL, ZALF, AWI, AgKiu, UCP, TI, SEGES, UniPG, SOL, APRIL, SOL	0%	0%	M 10	M xx	M 46	M xx	xx	xx
1.3	1.3.3	Capacity building for actors in legume production and valorization	Task xx	?	JHI, ADAS, DIL, ZALF, AWI, AgKiu, UCP, TI, SEGES, UniPG, SOL, APRIL, SOL	0%	0%	M 10	M xx	M 46	M xx	xx	xx
1.4	-	Promote legume benefits along the value chain	Task xx	?	CM, FIBL, DIL, AgKiu, ITC	0%	0%	M 13	M xx	M 48	M xx	xx	xx

WP xx will deliver the following outputs (i.e. products/processes/methods/...):													
Identifier	Application (Name)	Result Type	Output Type	Tangible format/Result	Lead partner	Availability			Comment	Progress beyond SotA			
						current	by M24	by M36					
WPT01.1.1.1	xxx	Process/ product ...	R, ER, KER?	Yes/No	name	0	0	0	xxx	xxx			
WPT01.1.1.2	0	Process/ product ...			name	0	0	0	0	xxx			
WPT01.1.1.3	0	Process/ product ...			name	0	0	0	0	xxx			
WPT01.1.1.4	0	Process/ product ...			name	0	0	0	0	xxx			

Figure 2. Screenshot of MS Office-based reporting tool for Work Package and Pilot Study leaders to report on the progress of their outputs - exemplary summary page of WP1.

Instructions:

(1) Before filling in this table make sure to read the info on the "INFO" tab first!!!
 (2) Complete one form for each Work Package Task (WPT) that is listed in the Work Package workplan.
 (3) Give each WPT a clear number - and use that number for the rest of the project.
 (4) Whenever you are asked to update your form, simply unhide the respective rows in the progress log.
 (5) Use the exact same form for all future reports and update sections where needed.

WP Task number: WP Subtask number: WP task name:

WP leader name: WP leader:

Task leader (LL): Task organisation:

Tasks (per DoA) to which this Work Package Task reports:

Partners involved (lead partner first):

Work Package task linkages:

Planned start month: Actual start month:

Planned end month: Actual end month:

Shortened task description as in WP workplan (max 200 words; basic material/methods, where and how the work will be carried out):

Subtask 1.1.1: A National Multactor Workshops (MAWS) will be held in each project-partner country in Y1 (MS1), inviting key stakeholders and actors in legume value chains, from production and processing to retail, research, and policy. This will coalesce existing legume-facing communities and industry networks and will build on previous legume projects. Stakeholders will be invited to prioritize their goals for increased legume production, and legume-associated ES valorization, and conceive future scenarios for legume use where the barriers and opportunities will be re-examined with respect to ES-valorization using SWOT analysis. The workshops will: i) identify new ways for actors to cooperate in each region through a Living Lab approach (LL: T1.1.2); ii) provide information about policies affecting legume uptake (T5.1/T5.2); and iii) identify knowledge gaps for capacity building (T1.3). Further iterative discussion with stakeholders will occur in WP1 (T1.3, T1.4) to evaluate project activities and findings.

Completeness (%): Risk (type 0 = red; 1 = amber; 2 = green):

0 = Red indicates that immediate remedial action is needed. **1 = Amber** is a warning that investigation and more detailed or more frequent monitoring is required. **2 = Green** is normal status.

Output/ product/process/method coming from the task (bullet points only):

Identifier	Application	Type / Output	Lead partner
WPT01.1.1.1	xxx	Process/ product ...	name
WPT01.1.1.2		Process/ product ...	name
WPT01.1.1.3		Process/ product ...	name
WPT01.1.1.4		Process/ product ...	name

Amount/number/etc. that will be produced of a certain CSTP... (bullet points only):

Identifier	Currently available	Available by M36	Available by M48	Comment
WPT01.1.1.1	0	0	0	xxx
WPT01.1.1.2				
WPT01.1.1.3				
WPT01.1.1.4				

Progress beyond State-of-the-Art for each WPT0:

xxx
xxx
xxx
xxx

Figure 3. Screenshot of MS Office-based reporting tool for Work Package and Pilot Study leaders to report on the progress of their outputs - exemplary summary page of Subtask 1.1.1 of WP1.

Report Month	WP	WP task	WP/ WPT linkages	Unique Output Identifier	Output type	Output Detail/description	Potential commercial product (Y/N/tbc)	Estimated completeness	Current TRL	M48 TRL	Expected start date	Actual start date	Expected complete date	Actual complete date	WP Leader name	WP Leader's organisation	WP Task leader name	WPT Leader's organisation	Comments	
			1.2 1.3	1.1.1	Process	Explanation what this output is / entails	Yes / No / to be decided	5%	4	5	6	6	48	48	Going well
12	1	1.1		1.2.1	Product
12	1	1.2		1.3.1	Software
12	1	1.3		1.4.1	Report
12	1	1.4																		

Figure 4. Screenshot of MS Excel-based Innovation Database filled with exemplary data.

3.1.2. Internal training to craft exploitation plans

Facilitating exploitation of results relies, to some degree, on fostering the appropriate mindset and deliver training to the project participants. During the kick-off-meeting, participants were informed about the necessity and benefits of exploitation to create impact. During **Exploitation Workshops** at General Assembly and online meetings, the IM will raise further awareness for and engage all WP and pilot study participants across the entire consortium in exploitation. This will start with a training in the use and functionality of the MS Office-based reporting tool and **Innovation Database** and lead to the initial identification of potential results. The IM will then help the IPR owners to progressively develop exploitation plans and prepare owners for potential commercialization of their results. Thus, further workshops will introduce a **business model canvas**, a SWOT, and a PESTLE (political, economic, social, and technological) analysis. This will culminate into an **Innovation Portfolio** (Deliverable7.5) which will detail all **Exploitation Plans** for **LegumES'** KERs. It will also lead to a gradual expansion of the information (see below) for each result in the **Innovation Database**, e.g.:

USP (unique selling point), potential impact, (industry) barriers addressed, related SDGs, expected improvement on economic / environmental /social sustainability if applied, industry relevance, expected likeliness of adoption (by industry) in less than 5 years, commercialisation, related projects / EU missions, related EC Policy Area, if applicable, potential policy that might be influenced by result, target groups, geographic target area, transferability to other areas/fields, exploitation mechanism, pathway / planned exploitation actions, message to potential user, timeline for exploitation, Key-Performance-Indicator (KPIs) (for exploitation activities), plans to create start-up, existing customers for the result, KER published on the Horizon Results Platform, existence of business plan / market studies / testimonials / references / scalable business model, replicability of result, long-term sustainability of business model, material available for investors, looking for investment of k€, further needs (We are Looking for), remaining technical challenges, any other information or comment.

3.1.3. IPR

All outputs generated are potentially subject to **Intellectual Property Rights** (IPR), and this aspect will be managed by an **IPR Management Team** (IPR-MT) comprising the Project Coordinator and exploitation manager (EM,) who will be supported by a trained **Senior Patent Engineer** (from the Knowledge and Technology Transfer Office at AWI).

The **IPR Management Team** led by the EM will use the Innovation Database to map all potential ERs and KERs and extend the information of the database including columns on:

- Result Contributors
- IPR Protection
- IP ownership
- IPR conflict
- Planned IPR conflict mitigation measures.

With this information, the IPR-MT will prepare an **IPR Conflict Prevention Plan**, listing all potential ERs and KERs whose ownership is shared (i.e., ERs/KERs with multiple contributors). The partners involved in each of these ER/KER will indicate their current plans for exploitation routes, identify possible

conflicts for successful exploitation and explore potential solutions together with the IPR Management team. This will ensure early detection of potential conflicts and elaborate early circumvention or solutions. The **IPR Conflict Prevention Plan** is a living document, that will be updated every 6 months using any new information from the Innovation Database. The IPR management does not constitute a legal service. If a legal service is sought by or proposed to partners, this will be pursued by the respective partner(s) themselves *via* professional (patent) lawyers.

The IPR-MT will also supervise partners' compliance with IPR provisions for use and dissemination as detailed in the DESCA-based Consortium Agreement, project publications, support of any patent registrations, and organize any other action relevant to protect IPR.

3.1.4. External tools and services for exploitation

In due course and depending on the nature of individual KER, the project will also make use of external tools and services offered by the EC to foster their exploitation. The EM will encourage partners to participate in these actions and engage with the relevant services. The following services are being considered for this purpose:

EC Free-of-charge services

The **Horizon Results Booster Services** offer expert support to accelerate the dissemination and exploitation potential of the most promising results. The **Horizon Results Booster (HRB)** is an initiative of the European Commission which aims to bring a continual stream of innovation to the market and maximise the impact of public funded research within the EU. It supports projects eager to go beyond their Dissemination and Exploitation obligations - steering research towards strong societal impact and concretising the value of Research and Innovation activity for societal challenges.

The Horizon Results Booster offers 3 types of free consulting services:

1. Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy
 - a. Identifying and creating the portfolio of Research & Innovation project results (module A),
 - b. Creating the portfolio of results; design and execute a portfolio dissemination plan (module B)
 - c. Improving existing exploitation strategy (module C)
2. Tailor made support services to develop a detailed business plan
3. Assistance, coaching and mentoring for go-to-market activities.

EC Free-of-charge tools

- [Horizon Result Platform](#): a tool for beneficiaries in disseminating their KERs, for stakeholders to engage with beneficiaries, directly or through NCP, and for the EC to learn from project results.
- [Research and Innovation success stories](#): a database of projects and success stories of EU-funded Research and Innovation
- [Horizon Results Booster success stories](#)

- [Cordis](#): the Commission’s database of EU-funded research and innovation projects (CORDIS).
– Find information on all public research projects funded by the EU under its framework programmes since the 1980s. Data includes participants, results, reports, deliverables, and links to open-access publications.
- [Horizon Dashboard](#): a powerful analytical tool for visualisation and analysis to explore project and proposal data and other related statistics. Here in particular the “[Project Results](#)” section which presents information on results of funded projects, notably Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) and scientific publications.
- [Innovation Radar](#): The Innovation Radar is a European Commission initiative to identify high potential innovations and innovators in EU-funded research and innovation projects.

4. Appendix 1: Communication Handbook

The Communication Handbook describes the communication tools and materials to be used by LegumES. It also includes communication guidelines that feature the Book of Style, Website and Social Media Guidelines, Translation Points, and materials ready to be used.

4.1. Communication Channels

To effectively reach our diverse target groups, the LegumES project will utilize a variety of communication channels.

Creative Minds operates the **website**, and **social media** as main channels. The website is considered the main information hub for the project, encapsulating the project's activities, news, and events. Combining a user-friendly interface with clear navigation to facilitate user experience, plus a modular approach that can adapt to the needs of the project, the platform also complements the [LegumES community](#) on Zenodo. All partners have been encouraged to follow the project's social media accounts and use the following hashtags when posting on those channels:

**#Legumes #Crops #Innovation #WildLegumes #ForgottenFood #CropDiversification
#OpportunityCrops**

These channels are:

[Official website](#)

[Official Facebook](#)

[Official Instagram](#)

[Official X](#)

[Official LinkedIn](#)

4.1.1. Offline communication: Poster/ Infographics/Leaflet

The creation of printed materials is crucial to create a recognisable brand and attract the attention of the unfamiliar audiences. Creative Minds will coordinate the preparation of posters, infographics, and brochures to accomplish the objectives outlined in the Communication Strategy, while accounting the resources resulting from the Dissemination plan. Visual materials will be made available through the website, Zenodo and the SharePoint for their broad usage in all project activities.

4.1.2. Audiovisual

Creative Minds will produce and edit 2 general promotion videos, followed by 3 additional videos of a shorter duration, intended for social media distribution as part of the Communication Strategy. Project partners will be expected to contribute from the very start. Creative Minds will perform interviews and record resources that can serve multiple messages throughout the different stages of the project, avoiding additional workload for the partners while complying with the objectives set in the communication strategy.

4.1.3. Translation of communication and dissemination materials

All materials and outputs will be produced in English. However, reaching out to broader audiences and working with local stakeholders will require translating key materials and messages. Hence, local partners will ensure LegumES is able to engage citizens locally and nationally. The communication and dissemination champion officer will oversee the translation of all relevant outputs in their national languages as listed below.

- Portuguese – UCP, UAver, CM
- French – TI
- German – DIL, AWI, PIK
- Italian – UNIPG
- Slovenian – ITC, JSI
- Hungarian – AgKu, ESSRG
- Macedonian - AGFT
- Spanish – APRI, SOL
- Danish – SEGES
- Swiss – FiBL, WBF
- Belgian - ARC

Wherever possible, translation to other Member States official languages will also be provided.

4.2. Templates

Templates for deliverables, reports, presentations, agenda and minutes have been produced and are available to all partners via the LegumES SharePoint ([LegumES - Templates](#)).

4.3. Funding Acknowledgements

LegumES is funded through multiple sources, as the consortium includes four associated partners in two countries (UK and Switzerland). Unlike the beneficiaries, they do not have access to the Horizon Europe funding; instead, funding is provided by Innovate UK and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation (SERI).

Different rules apply when acknowledging the funders and it is the responsibility of each participant to comply with these. Here is a brief explanation of the mandatory disclaimers.

- Funding must always appear in documents and communication materials produced by the project. In terms of appearance order, the European Union funding statement is prominent over any other. It is followed by the Innovate UK logo and grant number, then the SERI logo and grant number.

- In some cases, a responsibility disclaimer must accompany the funding statement. When in doubt, we will also encourage partners to use both. Here are the general requirements:

- communications on behalf of the project and promotional materials > Funding only, clearly visible;
- official reports and channels > Funding in covers and credits (reports), and either header or footer (channels); the responsibility disclaimer may appear separately to the funders but must be included;
- scientific publications > A dedicated section must highlight both the funding statement and the responsibility disclaimer.

Responsibility Disclaimer

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), European Research Executive Agency (REA) or Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). Neither the European Union nor any other granting authority can be held responsible for them.

4.4. Book of Style

A document to ensure consistency on project communication is available to all partners. It establishes and promotes the LegumES brand to facilitate identification. Hence, it contains guides for the logo and all the visual elements and is available on the LegumES SharePoint ([LegumES - Book of Style](#)).

4.5. Useful Contacts

Communication Managers: Joana Salgado (jsalgado@creative-minds.pt)
Ana Ramião (aramiao@creative-minds.pt)

Exploitation Manager: Björn Suckow (bjoern.suckow@awi.de)

Project Manager: Fanny Tran (fanny.tran@hutton.ac.uk)
WP1 Leader: Ali Karley (ali.karley@hutton.ac.uk)

Project Coordinator: Pietro Iannetta (iannetta@ucp.pt)

5. Appendix 2: Guidelines and templates for dissemination materials

This annex provides an overview of the guidelines provided to partners regarding the various dissemination tools (i.e., publications, conference and event presentations, practice abstracts, factsheets, tutorials, podcasts, infographics, and policy briefs) that will be used as part as LegumES dissemination plan to widely disseminate the project results and outputs (Table 5).

Table 5. Summary of key information for LegumES dissemination materials.

Dissemination Activity	Add to tracker (section 8.2.1)	Sharepoint for review ²	~ total partner time required	Workflow	~ time for workflow	More info in section
Peer-reviewed and scientific publications	“Publications” tab	30 days before submission	--	Draft → upload to SharePoint and add to tracker → submit → add accepted version of the manuscript to Zenodo → update tracker	--	5.2.1
Publications in non-scientific outlets	“Publications” tab	14 days before submission	--	Draft → upload to SharePoint and add to tracker → publish → upload to Zenodo → update tracker	--	5.2.2
Conference (or other event) presentations	“Dissemination Activities” tab	21 days before submission	--	Draft → upload to SharePoint and add to tracker → present at conference → upload outputs to Zenodo → update tracker	--	5.2.3
LegumES Events	“Dissemination Activities” tab	3-4 months before event	5 - 7 days per event	Add to tracker → define format and structure (include CM and HUTTON) → define workflow within team → upload concept to SharePoint → review by CM and HUTTON → online promotion (CM) → hold the event → update tracker	>4 weeks	5.2.4
Practice abstracts and associated Factsheets	“Dissemination Material” tab	14 days before publication	2.5 days per practice abstract	Add to tracker → draft → revisions by coordination team → rounds of revision → format (HUTTON) → upload to SharePoint (HUTTON) → submit to EIP-Agri (HUTTON) → publish (CM) → update tracker	>12 weeks	5.2.5
Tutorial videos	“Dissemination Material” tab	Upload concept 14 days before recording	2-4 days per tutorial	Add to tracker → define video production team (include CM) → define workflow within team → upload concept to SharePoint → review by CM and HUTTON → publish (CM) → update tracker	>7 weeks	5.2.6

Dissemination Activity	Add to tracker (section 8.2.1)	Sharepoint for review ²	~ total partner time required	Workflow	~ time for workflow	More info in section
Podcasts	“Dissemination Material” tab	Upload concept 14 days before recording	1.5-3 days per podcast	Add to tracker → create concept and organize recording → send to CM and HUTTON for revision and upload concept to SharePoint → record podcast → edit podcast → review by CM and coordination team → publish → update tracker	>8 weeks	5.2.7
Infographics	“Dissemination Material” tab	14 days before publication	1 day per infographic	Add to tracker → create concept → graphic design (CM) → upload to SharePoint (CM) → publish → update tracker	>8 weeks	5.2.8
Policy briefs	“Dissemination Material” tab	21 days before publication	3.5 days per policy brief	Add to tracker → draft → revisions to coordination team → rounds of revision → format (CM) → upload to SharePoint (CM) → submit to EIP-Agri (HUTTON) → publish (CM) → update tracker	>14 weeks	5.2.9

5.1. Dissemination tracking and implementation of the dissemination plan

Partners are expected to use the Excel “[Tracker](#)” available on the project SharePoint. This tracker is used as a tool to track partners’ participation in conferences and other events, and publication of peer-reviewed and non-peer-reviewed articles. This will also be used to follow the workflow of other dissemination materials. The tracker comprises 4 tabs:

1. **Publications** for partners to log all articles submitted in peer-reviewed journals and non-peer-reviewed magazines.
2. **Dissemination Activities** for partners to register their participation at international and national/regional events.
3. **Dissemination Materials** serves as a tracker of the workflow of dissemination materials, where all practice abstracts, tutorials, podcast episodes, infographics and policy briefs will be scheduled.
4. **Communications** for partners to report any communication activities they have taken part in such as TV/radio interviews, newsletters, press releases, leaflets, social media campaign etc.

The information requested in each tab mirrors the information that must be entered in the EU portal in each periodic report. More information, including tool descriptions, responsibilities, timelines, workflow, and links to templates is provided in the sections below.

5.2. Dissemination tools, timelines, and workflows

5.2.1. Peer-reviewed and scientific publications

Description																
<p>A minimum of <u>30 days</u> before submission of an article to a scientific journal, a draft of the finalized text must be uploaded on the LegumES Sharepoint under WP1 > Communication and Dissemination > Forms to fill > Article for Review. During these 30 days, partners have the opportunity to review the article, even if they were not directly involved. Partners will automatically be notified by SharePoint once an article has been uploaded to the above folder.</p> <p>After the 30-day-review-period, the manuscript can be submitted to the journal. Once it is accepted, the first author must upload the accepted version to Zenodo and record the date and Zenodo-URL on the LegumES Tracker (Publication Tab) to ensure immediate open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications. This is a new obligation, beneficiaries must follow in the Horizon Europe programme. Once it is published on the journal website, the first author must update the Tracker with the journal-url (Publication Tab).</p> <p>Please note that <i>'Only publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.'</i></p> <p>Partners are also reminded that scientific publications can be published through the Open Research Europe platform, an open access, publishing platform for scientific papers for Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe beneficiaries, which features an open peer review and article revision procedure.</p>																
Responsibilities																
<p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Upload draft to SharePoint for review Upload accepted manuscript to Zenodo Update Tracker (Publication Tab) 	<p>Consortium</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review the draft 	<p>CM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promotion and Dissemination 														
Timeline																
<p>The timeline and workflow are rough estimates and will vary from case to case. Allocated time refers to the total amount of time needed to complete each task.</p>																
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Allocated Time</th> <th>-</th> <th>30 days</th> <th>7 days</th> <th>~ 3 month</th> <th>1 day</th> <th>End</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <th>Task</th> <td>Upload draft to SharePoint</td> <td>Review</td> <td>Submit to Journal</td> <td>Review by Journal</td> <td>Upload accepted manuscript to Zenodo</td> <td>Update tracker</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Allocated Time	-	30 days	7 days	~ 3 month	1 day	End	Task	Upload draft to SharePoint	Review	Submit to Journal	Review by Journal	Upload accepted manuscript to Zenodo	Update tracker		
Allocated Time	-	30 days	7 days	~ 3 month	1 day	End										
Task	Upload draft to SharePoint	Review	Submit to Journal	Review by Journal	Upload accepted manuscript to Zenodo	Update tracker										
Template	Contact															
NA	Fanny Tran: fanny.tran@hutton.ac.uk															

5.2.2. Publications in non-scientific outlets

Description																
<p>A minimum of 14 days before the submission of an article to a non-scientific outlet, a draft of the finalized text must be uploaded on the LegumES Sharepoint under WP1 > Communication and Dissemination > Forms to fill > Article for Review. During these 14 days, partners have the opportunity to review the article, even if they were not involved before. Partners will automatically be notified by SharePoint once an article has been uploaded to the above folder.</p> <p>After the 14-day-review-period, the article can be submitted to the magazine. Once the article is accepted, the first author must upload the article to Zenodo and record the date and Zenodo-URL on the LegumES Tracker (Publication Tab).</p>																
Responsibilities																
<p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload draft to SharePoint for review • Upload published manuscript to Zenodo • Update Tracker (Publication Tab) 	<p>Consortium</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review the draft 	<p>CM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion and Dissemination 														
Timeline																
<p>The timeline and workflow are rough estimates and will vary from case to case. Allocated time refers to the total amount of time needed to complete each task.</p>																
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Allocated Time</th> <th>-</th> <th>14 days</th> <th>7 days</th> <th>~ 1 month</th> <th>1 day</th> <th>End</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <th>Task</th> <td>Upload draft to SharePoint</td> <td>Review</td> <td>Submit to Journal</td> <td>Review by Magazine</td> <td>Upload final manuscript to Zenodo</td> <td>Update tracker</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Allocated Time	-	14 days	7 days	~ 1 month	1 day	End	Task	Upload draft to SharePoint	Review	Submit to Journal	Review by Magazine	Upload final manuscript to Zenodo	Update tracker		
Allocated Time	-	14 days	7 days	~ 1 month	1 day	End										
Task	Upload draft to SharePoint	Review	Submit to Journal	Review by Magazine	Upload final manuscript to Zenodo	Update tracker										
Template	Contact															
NA	<p>Joana Salgado: jsalgado@creative-minds.pt Fanny Tran: fanny.tran@hutton.ac.uk</p>															

5.2.3. Conference (or other event) presentations

Description																
<p>A minimum of 21 days before submission of an abstract for a conference, a draft of the finalized text must be uploaded on the LegumES SharePoint under WP1 > Communication and Dissemination > Forms to fill > Article for Review. During these 21 days, partners have the opportunity to review the abstract. Partners will automatically be notified by SharePoint once an article has been uploaded to the above folder.</p> <p>After the 21-days-review-period, the abstract can be submitted to the conference. Once the abstract is accepted, the first author must upload the abstract to Zenodo and record the date and Zenodo-URL on the LegumES Tracker (Dissemination Activities Tab).</p>																
Responsibilities																
<p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload draft to SharePoint for review • Upload abstracts, posters/slides to Zenodo • Fill in Tracker (Dissemination Activities Tab) 	<p>Consortium</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review the draft 	<p>CM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion and Dissemination 														
Timeline																
<p>The timeline and workflow are rough estimates and will vary from case to case. Allocated time refers to the total amount of time needed to complete each task.</p>																
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Allocated Time</th> <th>-</th> <th>21 days</th> <th>7 days</th> <th>~ 1 month</th> <th>1 day</th> <th>End</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <th>Task</th> <td>Upload draft to SharePoint</td> <td>Review</td> <td>Submit to conference</td> <td>Review by conference</td> <td>Upload abstract and poster to Zenodo</td> <td>Update tracker</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Allocated Time	-	21 days	7 days	~ 1 month	1 day	End	Task	Upload draft to SharePoint	Review	Submit to conference	Review by conference	Upload abstract and poster to Zenodo	Update tracker		
Allocated Time	-	21 days	7 days	~ 1 month	1 day	End										
Task	Upload draft to SharePoint	Review	Submit to conference	Review by conference	Upload abstract and poster to Zenodo	Update tracker										
Template	Contact															
NA	<p>Joana Salgado: jsalgado@creative-minds.pt Fanny Tran: fanny.tran@hutton.ac.uk</p>															

5.2.4. LegumES events

Description		
<p>LegumES will organize its own events, e.g., National Multiactor Workshops, Tasting-Cocreation Workshops, National Cooperation Workshops, Innovation Camps, international symposium organized to disseminate the project results. These will be targeted at different audiences. Guidelines for each of these events will be available for all event organizers on SharePoint.</p>		
Responsibilities		
<p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define format and structure • Organise logistics • Translations • Write summary report • Fill in the Tracker (Dissemination Activities Tab) 	<p>HUTTON</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide guidance and templates • Technical support 	<p>CM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote the event
Timeline		
<p>The timeline and workflow are rough estimates and will vary from case to case. Allocated time refers to the total amount of time needed to complete each task.</p>		
Template	Contact	
NA	<p>Ali Karley: ali.karley@hutton.ac.uk Joana Salgado: jsalgado@creative-minds.pt Fanny Tran: fanny.tran@hutton.ac.uk</p>	

5.2.5. Practice Abstracts and associated factsheets

Description		
<p>The practice abstracts are short and concise practical information to farmers, advisors, and other target groups. They facilitate knowledge exchange and contact between potential partners in innovative projects. The practice abstracts will be published on the EIP-AGRI Project Database, which features innovative projects from across Europe that boost innovation and knowledge exchange for agriculture, forestry and rural areas.</p> <p>Practice Abstracts will then be turned into factsheets summarizing key project results of relevance to agricultural practice, targeting, farmers, farm advisors, and other stakeholders. These factsheets will include photographs, infographics, or illustrations and will be structured as follows: 1. problem; 2. solution; 3. outcome; 4. recommendations.</p>		
Responsibilities		
<p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw text in Word template, min. 13 weeks before the due date • Provision of pictures/illustrations • Text Revisions • Dissemination through own network • Registration of workflow in the Tracker (Dissemination materials tab) 	<p>HUTTON</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Text editing • Layout and Illustrations • Upload on SharePoint • Upload to EIP-Agri and Zenodo 	<p>CM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disseminate widely
Timeline		
<p>The timeline and workflow are rough estimates and will vary from case to case. Allocated time refers to the total amount of time needed to complete each task.</p>		
<pre> graph LR A[Allocated Time] --- B[Task] B --> C[Writing the raw text, provide photo] C --> D[Editing HUTTON] D --> E[Revise Draft] E --> F[Finalise HUTTON] F --> G[Submit to EIP-Agri and upload to Zenodo HUTTON] G --> H[Promote and Disseminate CM] H --> I[End] </pre>		
Template		Contact
<p>LegumES Practice Abstracts Template</p>		<p>Fanny Tran: fanny.tran@hutton.ac.uk</p>

5.2.6. Tutorial videos

Description	
<p>Tutorial videos can have different formats, depending on the purpose and target audience. The format (tutorial, story-telling in PPT, etc.) for each video is agreed upon in the consensus meeting or at the latest when finalizing the concept of the video. The target audience of these videos can be practitioners (e.g., farmers, breeders, advisors), the scientific community, policymakers, or the general public. Guidelines describing video styles, preparation and concept creation, equipment and editing are available to all partners on SharePoint.</p>	
Responsibilities	
<p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide ideas for content • Lead on the concept of the video • Text for A-roll, interview questions • Produce video according to the guidelines • Video editing (where possible) • Subtitles when translated into another language • Registration of workflow in the Tracker (Dissemination materials tab) 	<p>FIBL and CM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical support (guidelines, training, standardized look and feel) • Support with text, concept and editing • Promotion and dissemination • Upload to Zenodo
Timeline	
<p>The timeline and workflow will vary depending on what kind of video is being produced. For all videos, make sure to start at least eight weeks before it needs to be finished. You should also:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • inform FiBL, CM and HUTTON before starting; • create a concept (see guidelines); • upload concept to SharePoint WP1 > Communication and Dissemination > Forms to fill > Article for Review 14 days prior to filming; and, • allow enough time for the coordination team to review the concept as well as the final video. 	
Template	Contact
NA	<p>Matthias Klaiss: matthias.klaiss@fibl.org Joana Salgado: jsalgado@creative-minds.pt Fanny Tran: fanny.tran@hutton.ac.uk</p>

5.2.7. Podcasts

Description	
<p>Podcasts can have different formats, depending on the purpose and target audience. The format (interview, panel discussion, technical note) for each podcast episode is agreed upon in the consensus meeting or at the latest when finalizing the podcast concept. Podcasts can be recorded live or remotely, e.g., with the software Iris FM. Guidelines describing podcast styles, preparation and concept creation, equipment, editing, and language are available to all partners on SharePoint.</p>	
Responsibilities	
<p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide ideas for content • Lead on the concept of the podcast • Text for the technical note or interview questions • Podcast editing (where possible) • Translations • Registration of workflow in Tracker (Dissemination materials tab) 	<p>CM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical support (guidelines, software for recording and transcript) • Support with text, concept and editing • Upload to Zenodo • Promotion and dissemination
Timeline	
<p>The timeline and workflow are rough estimates and will vary from case to case. Allocated time refers to the total amount of time needed to complete each task.</p>	
<pre> graph LR A[Allocated Time] --- B[Task] B --> C[Create a concept and organise the recording (Podcast Team) - 2 weeks] C --> D[Review the concept (HUTTON) - 2 weeks] D --> E[Record Podcast - 1 week] E --> F[Edit Podcast - 2 weeks] F --> G[Review and Validate (HUTTON) - 2 weeks] G --> H[Upload to Zenodo (HUTTON)] H --> I[Promote and Disseminate (CM)] </pre>	
Template	Contact
NA	<p>Joana Salgado: jsalgado@creative-minds.pt Fanny Tran: fanny.tran@hutton.ac.uk</p>

5.2.8. Infographics

Description	
<p>Infographics are visual representations of information or data. They should include only minimal text and give an easy-to-understand overview of a topic. Infographics can be used to provide an overview of a topic; explain a complex process or environment or showcase research findings.</p> <p>An infographic can be integrated into an article, factsheet, video, website, or social media post. All LegumES infographics have to follow the guidelines of the LegumES Book of Style.</p>	
Responsibilities	
<p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide ideas for content a minimum of six weeks before it is due • Lead on the concept of the infographic • Registration of workflow in the tracker • Use in LegumES outputs 	<p>CM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the production of infographics • Upload to Zenodo
Timeline	
<p>The timeline and workflow are rough estimates and will vary from case to case. Allocated time refers to the total amount of time needed to complete each task.</p>	
<pre> graph LR subgraph Allocated Time A1[2 days] A2[4 weeks] A3[4 weeks] A4[2 weeks] A5[2 weeks] A6[2 weeks] end subgraph Task T1[Create concept] --> T2[Finalise the concept (CM & HUTTON)] T2 --> T3[Create Infographics (CM)] T3 --> T4[Review and Validate (HUTTON)] T4 --> T5[Upload to Zenodo (HUTTON)] T5 --> T6[Promote and Disseminate (CM)] end A1 --- T1 A2 --- T2 A3 --- T3 A4 --- T4 A5 --- T5 A6 --- T6 </pre>	
Template	Contact
NA	<p>Joana Salgado: jsalgado@creative-minds.pt</p> <p>Fanny Tran: fanny.tran@hutton.ac.uk</p>

5.2.9. Policy briefs

Description																								
<p>Policy briefs are short documents that present findings and recommendations of a research project to government policymakers and others, who are interested in formulating or influencing policy. There are two types of policy briefs: 1. advocacy briefs that argue in favour of a particular course of action and 2. objective briefs that provide balanced information. A policy brief should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ... be short, to the point, and focus on a particular problem or issue. It should provide enough information to understand the issue and come to a decision. • ... be based on firm evidence, not just one or two experiments or a single year’s experience. It should draw evidence from various sources – preferably from several different areas or organizations. • ... focus on meanings, not methods. Readers are interested in what the researchers found and recommended. They do not need to know methodological details. • ... relate to the big picture. The policy brief may build on context-specific findings, but it should draw conclusions that are more generally applicable but, at the same time, assure that it does not become too general but remains concrete in recommendations. 																								
Responsibilities																								
<p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw text in Word template, min. 14 weeks before the due date • Provision of pictures and concepts for illustrations • Text revisions • Disseminating to relevant contacts 	<p>ESSRG</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Text editing • Layout and illustrations 	<p>CM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload on the SharePoint • Upload to Zenodo and other relevant platforms 																						
Timeline																								
<p>The timeline and workflow are rough estimates and will vary from case to case. Allocated time refers to the total amount of time needed to complete each task.</p>																								
<table border="1"> <tr> <td style="background-color: #2e4c3e; color: white;">Allocated Time</td> <td style="background-color: #2e4c3e; color: white;">2 days</td> <td style="background-color: #2e4c3e; color: white;">8 weeks</td> <td style="background-color: #2e4c3e; color: white;">2 weeks</td> <td style="background-color: #2e4c3e; color: white;">End</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="background-color: #2e4c3e; color: white;">Task</td> <td style="background-color: #2e4c3e; color: white;">Write raw text</td> <td style="background-color: #2e4c3e; color: white;">Edit Text (ESSRG)</td> <td style="background-color: #2e4c3e; color: white;">Review draft</td> <td style="background-color: #2e4c3e; color: white;">Finalise (ESSRG)</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td style="background-color: #2e4c3e; color: white;">Upload to Zenodo (CM)</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td style="background-color: #2e4c3e; color: white;">Promote and Disseminate (CM)</td> </tr> </table>	Allocated Time	2 days	8 weeks	2 weeks	End	Task	Write raw text	Edit Text (ESSRG)	Review draft	Finalise (ESSRG)					Upload to Zenodo (CM)					Promote and Disseminate (CM)				
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				Promote and Disseminate (CM)																				
Template	Contact																							
NA	<p>Bálint Balázs: balazs.balint@essrg.hu Joana Salgado: jsalgado@creative-minds.pt</p>																							